

УДК 372.881.1

INTEGRATING AI TOOLS INTO PROFESSIONALLY ORIENTED FOREIGN LANGUAGE COURSES

IRINA ROGOVA

associate professor of the Department of Foreign Languages for special purposes of the Dostoevsky Omsk State University, Omsk, Russia

Abstract: *The article analyzes the key areas of AI application, in particular, personalization of learning, development of speech skills and gamification; special attention is paid to practical cases of using the AI platforms DeepSeek and GigaChat for generating educational materials. The purpose of this article is to analyze the possibilities of integrating artificial intelligence (AI) into teaching foreign languages using interactive AI tools (DeepSeek, GigaChat, etc.), adapting educational materials to the professional needs of students (for example, IT specialists) and increasing their motivation. The role of the teacher who selects and adapts educational materials is emphasized. The article presents the developed methodological recommendations for the selection and modification of materials generated by AI, taking into account pedagogical goals. The given examples demonstrate the significant potential of using digital technologies to improve the efficiency and quality of teaching: for foreign language teachers, this is time saving due to the automation of routine tasks, personalization and adaptation of tasks to specific professional areas and level of language proficiency, which facilitates the preparation of educational materials; the inclusion of interactive tools expands the possibilities of teaching practice, contributes to the development of students' oral speech, more effective assimilation of material, growth of motivation and involvement, development of professional skills and comprehensive development of competencies in demand in the modern labor market, makes learning more exciting. The article provides examples of CLIL integration into professionally oriented courses, systematizes successful practices for teachers implementing AI in the study of foreign languages, builds a connection between technological capabilities and pedagogical tasks, which is a relevant response to the demands of the digital age.*

Key words and phrases: *artificial intelligence (AI) in education; English as a Foreign Language / English as a Second Language; English for Special Purposes; Content and Language Integrated Learning; education technologies.*

In recent years, the education system has been undergoing large-scale transformations driven by increasing demands for the quality of specialist training, the need to account for individual student characteristics, and digitalization. One of the key drivers of these changes has been artificial intelligence (AI), which is being actively integrated into various areas of the educational process, including foreign language teaching.

To evaluate the possibilities of using AI in foreign language teaching, it is necessary to:

Analyze modern AI tools, examine their functionality and potential for language education, and determine which tasks can be automated.

Provide recommendations on the effective use of AI to optimize teachers' workload when preparing for classes.

Investigate how proposed solutions can account for students' proficiency levels, educational needs, and interests; explore approaches to integrating adaptive learning pathways into traditional courses to enable AI-powered personalized learning.

Study students' demands (e.g., from IT professionals) for specialized language content; create templates for generating profession-oriented tasks, adapting learning materials to professional needs.

Propose AI-enhanced interactive assignments to develop linguistic skills.

Develop engaging lesson formats through AI-generated ideas adapted by the instructor.

The study examined AI tools for teachers (MagicSchool.AI, Eduaide.AI, TeachMateAI, Curipod, etc.) on language learning platforms, alongside the author's practical experience of

implementing AI (DeepSeek, GigaChat) in teaching profession-specific English to IT undergraduates (3rd/4th year).

The theoretical framework was based on academic publications and research, including works on the integration of AI in education with an analysis of trends in the use of AI for EFL/ESL [Dudeney & Hockly, 2022] and the role of AI in personalizing learning [Luckin et al., 2022], as well as empirical studies on teacher workload and automated tasks [McKinsey, 2020] and reviews of the effectiveness of AI platforms [Godwin-Jones, 2022; Kukulska-Hulme, 2023].

The methodological framework of the study was based on the communicative approach [Hymes, 1972; Ait Hattani, 2021], the principles of Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) [Dzulkurnain & Iskandar, 2024], and Task-Based Learning (TBL) [Willis, 1996], implemented through AI-assisted practical tasks.

The research employed a mixed-methods approach, blending theoretical analysis with empirical testing. The initial phase involved evaluating AI tools' accuracy in generating targeted exercises (e.g., discourse marker activities for B1–B2 learners). Subsequently, tailored AI materials (such as First Conditional-based debates) were implemented in classrooms, with efficacy measured via comparative student performance analysis. Learner feedback was also systematically collected to assess perceptions of the AI-enhanced tasks and personalized methodology.

The findings highlight AI and digital technologies' potential to improve learning outcomes for both teachers and students. For instructors, AI saves time by automating tasks like exercise generation, reducing workload and allowing more focus on creative teaching strategies. The study provides templates for profession-specific personalized tasks and AI-content adaptation algorithms, facilitating level-adjusted material preparation.

Discussion and Results

A 2020 McKinsey survey conducted in collaboration with Microsoft, involving over 2,000 teachers in Canada, Singapore, the UK, and the US, revealed that educators work approximately 50 hours per week, with this figure increasing by 3% over the past five years. The study found that teachers spent less time on direct instruction and student interaction than on preparation, grading, and administrative tasks—with 20 to 40% of their workweek (around 13 hours) dedicated to activities that could be automated using existing technologies [Bryant et al., 2020].

Teachers work about 50 hours a week, spending less than half of the time in direct interaction with students.

Activity composition of teacher working hours, number of hours

¹ Average for respondents in Canada, Singapore, United Kingdom, and United States.

² Includes a small "other" category.

Source: McKinsey Global Teacher and Student Survey

McKinsey
 & Company

Contemporary research and international experience demonstrate that AI can significantly enhance the effectiveness of language education by automating routine tasks, personalizing learning pathways, expanding opportunities for interactive learning, and providing immediate feedback [Dudeney, G., & Hockly, N., 2022; Kukulska-Hulme, A., 2023]. Thanks to advancements

in adaptive platforms, intelligent assistants, and analytical tools, educators gain new resources for tailoring instruction, while learners benefit from self-paced study and personalized recommendations that address their individual strengths and weaknesses.

The following presents the main directions for implementing AI in foreign language instruction, drawing on contemporary research and expert recommendations in the field of language pedagogy:

Personalized Learning and Adaptive Educational Pathways

AI-powered platforms (Duolingo, Babbel, Rosetta Stone) utilize adaptive algorithms to tailor learning materials according to learners' language proficiency, cognitive characteristics, and developmental needs. This approach enables targeted practice of challenging areas (e.g., grammatical structures or lexical gaps) and ensures progress at an individual pace, thereby fostering linguistic confidence [Kukulska-Hulme, A., 2023].

Additionally, AI systems analyze student performance data to generate personalized exercises addressing common difficulties (e.g., verb tense usage, phonetic challenges) [EFL Cafe, 2024, November 15].

Interactive Development of Speaking and Listening Skills

Conversational AI agents (e.g., ChatGPT) simulate authentic communication scenarios, allowing learners to practice speech skills in near-real-life conditions. These systems can be adapted to various sociocultural contexts (e.g., everyday conversations or professional interactions), thereby fostering discursive competence [Godwin-Jones, R., 2022].

Integrated speech recognition systems provide instant feedback on pronunciation accuracy, intonation patterns, and speech rhythm, enhancing phonetic skills and auditory perception [EFL Cafe, 2024, November 15; EFL Cafe, 2024].

Automated Monitoring and Assessment of Learning Outcomes

AI-powered writing analysis tools (Grammarly, Cambridge Write & Improve) provide detailed corrective feedback on grammatical, stylistic, and lexical errors, as well as issues with text organization and logical flow. This immediate feedback enables learners to promptly address gaps in their language proficiency [Daud et al., 2025].

Optimizing Lesson Design and Curriculum Integration

AI technologies enable the development of tailored learning materials that align with specific pedagogical objectives (developing receptive and productive skills, expanding vocabulary) while accounting for learners' proficiency levels and professional contexts (ESP). Adaptive algorithms facilitate the creation of dynamic syllabi that accommodate diverse learner needs within heterogeneous groups [Dudeney, G., & Hockly, N., 2022].

Furthermore, AI can generate thematically relevant instructional materials by analyzing individual learning trajectories, thereby enhancing overall teaching effectiveness [EFL Cafe, 2024, November 15].

Enhancing Learning Motivation Through Gamification

The integration of game mechanics (achievement systems, leaderboards, virtual rewards) into AI-powered platforms helps sustain learners' cognitive engagement and fosters consistent language practice habits [Holmes, W., Bialik, M., & Fadel, C., 2019].

The comprehensive integration of AI solutions into foreign language instruction enables:

- Personalization by addressing learners' cognitive-linguistic profiles,
- Enhanced feedback quality and immediacy,
- Optimized time management for educators,
- Strengthened learner motivation.

The progression of language teaching methodology will depend on synergistic integration of educators' professional competence and AI's technological potential, with the latter serving in an auxiliary capacity without replacing the instructor's fundamental role.

However, despite the obvious advantages, the introduction of AI into language education is associated with a number of challenges: solving technical issues and ensuring digital equality, observing ethical standards and protecting personal data, the need to rethink the role of the teacher

and ensuring professional development of the teaching staff. In addition, the question remains about which aspects of learning can be automated and which remain solely the responsibility of the teacher - motivation, support, development of critical thinking and communication skills [Luckin et al., 2022].

Most popular AI teaching tools – such as MagicSchool.AI, Eduaide.AI, TeachMateAI, Curipod, Canva (including Magic Write and Classroom Magic), Gradescope, Otter.ai – have free versions or trial periods and are available for use from Russia. As for ChatGPT and Khanmigo, direct access from Russia is limited. Thus, this article explores successful practices and tools for integrating the capabilities of neural network platforms DeepSeek and GigaChat that are open and free unlimitedly to optimize educational processes. Special attention is given to analyzing practical cases, particularly the author's firsthand experience in implementing AI tools for teaching Professional English, along with developing actionable guidelines for educators seeking to effectively harness new technologies in language instruction.

The requests to AI platforms analyzed in the article can be divided into several categories:

- generating ideas for specific educational goals,
- solving practical educational problems,
- adapting educational tasks and materials (to the specifics of the group).

It should be emphasized that the use of AI agents to **generate ideas for specific purposes** involves choosing from all the proposed options the one that best suits the educational goals and can be adapted to a specific group of students, i.e. the teacher is responsible for selecting and adapting the options proposed by the AI. Several such requests can be given as an example.

Creating a list of Ice-Breaking Activities for A2 ESL learners: the learning goals were to create conditions for students to get to know each other, identify their language level, and form initial team interactions. To achieve these goals, two of the tasks proposed by the AI were selected and adapted:

1. Interview and introduction. Students are divided into pairs for the interview and use a prepared list of questions (e.g., "Where are you from?"). After the interview, each student introduces their partner.

For the purpose of scaffolding, the most common and then the most tricky questions asked during introductions were written on the board as part of the group discussion. Students were oriented to the fact that they could use both the discussed preparations and their own options in the interview. After the time given for the interview, a stage of introducing classmates was held taking into account the previously agreed task: to tell the most important and most interesting things about the partner. Analysis of the results showed that the use of this strategy contributed to achieving the goals of introduction, removing communication barriers, and primary diagnostics of language skills. In addition, the development of listening and speaking skills under conditions of minimal emotional pressure was noted.

2. True or false. Procedure: each student prepares three personal statements: two true and one false; students take turns sharing their statements and guessing which one is false.

The rules of this game element of the lesson were taken unchanged: students were given time to prepare statements about themselves, after which, in a group, students took turns sharing their information, and the rest guessed which one was false. This task promotes the development of critical thinking and speaking practice, develops self-presentation and listening comprehension skills. To challenge the more advanced students, the group was asked to supply explanations—when possible—supporting the truth or falsity of the statements alongside their arguments.

The AI-generated ideas enabled the development of an effective lesson strategy: in the new group, everyone was able to get to know each other in an active format using a foreign language, and it was also possible to determine (based on the analysis of errors and difficulties that arose) the level of the students and the upcoming learning tasks.

Another example of generating ideas for specific learning tasks is a request for ideas for a lesson about Christmas and New Year and their traditions in English-speaking countries, which was used to

deepen students' understanding of another culture and expand their language skills. The following ideas were selected and adapted for these tasks:

1. Discussion on Christmas and New Year cultural traditions. Objective: To explore Christmas and New Year traditions in different English-speaking countries and compare them with the traditions of the students' home countries. For this purpose, a short presentation of the main traditions (e.g. Christmas dinners, Christmas carols, gifts) in countries such as the UK, USA, Canada and Australia was prepared. This was followed by a group discussion in which the students shared the holiday traditions of their home countries and compared them with the traditions of English-speaking countries. This task, in addition to improving language skills, allowed the students to develop intercultural competence, in particular, to overcome stereotypes about the similarity of traditions, strengthened reflection skills and group dynamics.

2. Festive music and singing together. Objective: to improve listening comprehension skills and broaden cultural awareness through music. According to the task, students guessed the names of the most popular Christmas carols, read their lyrics out loud, analyzed unknown fragments and words, and finally sang together verses from those carols that the students especially liked. The original goal of the task - the development of linguistic and socio-cultural competencies through the unique advantages of the musical format - was definitely achieved, as well as some bonus benefits, such as strengthened pronunciation and rhythm through singing, reinforced vocabulary in memorable, contextualized way, built group cohesion through shared musical experience.

3. Presentation of New Year's traditions. Objective: to learn about New Year's customs. The task was adapted for greater involvement and independent work of students: students in groups had to research unique New Year's traditions of different countries using pre-selected and provided links to Internet materials. After preparing the task, each group presented their most interesting findings, which contributed to the development of skills in researching authentic materials, public speaking, as well as the practice of active listening during the presentations of other groups and understanding of cultural differences and features.

4. Making a Christmas card. Objective: to use vocabulary for writing greeting cards. To complete this task, it was agreed with the students in advance that everyone would have to bring a new card to the lesson. Before the end of the lesson, the students wrote their greetings and wishes in English; after completing the preparatory stage, by blindly pulling out of a Christmas stocking, each student received their gift - a card with wishes from a classmate. In the group where the students were not unable to bring cards, this task was adapted as follows: stickers were used, on which the students wrote their wishes for each other and stuck them on the board (task name "Make a wish - take a wish"), and before leaving the classroom, they could take any wish from the board for themselves. A high degree of creativity in the wording of the greetings, as well as a positive emotional response from the participants, were noted.

Another example of AI assistance in generating ideas that has shown high application results is a request for forms of the final project in English in a group of IT specialists. The final project was a mandatory element of the final assessment for the course. Students were offered a list of options from which they could choose the one that best suited their interests and level of training, subject to approval by the teacher.

Of the 10 AI-generated options, most students preferred:

- Creating a report with an analysis of the topic, presenting their findings and recommendations, diagrams and illustrations, as well as explanations in English in the form of an oral presentation.
- A video presentation that talks about the project in English: this could be either a simple video with an explanation or screencasts demonstrating the operation of a program or application.
- Presenting your own developed software product - software or an application - in English, including code, instructions for use, technical specifications and user documentation.
- Creating a training video explaining a certain concept or process in English, providing an description of the algorithms and practical advice.

For each of the selected formats, assessment scales were developed and approved together with the students. All students were able to choose a project format adapted to their interests, level of language knowledge, which allowed them to demonstrate their strengths (coding, design, analytics) and pump up their weaknesses (lack of language training, fear of public speaking). The results of the practical work showed success in developing professional language competencies and soft skills (critical thinking, time management, creativity, communication skills). Such projects are significant because they close the gap between language learning and the real requirements of the IT market, making English a tool, not a goal. Some students reported that they were going to use the finished projects when applying for a job as part of their portfolio.

Examples of working with AI agents to **solve practical educational problems.**

After covering the topic of linking discourse markers, there arose a need to reinforce this material through interactive communicative practice in an engaging context for students (request: Create an activity to work with linking discourse markers with B1 B2 level students). The AI offered several task options, from which the following was selected and adapted:

Our teaching material required students to memorize the connecting discourse markers of informal and formal styles (though – whereas, just as – similarly, etc.). First, students were given the task of writing the beginning of sentences on different topics in groups, accompanying them with informal discourse markers, without completing the sentences. The groups exchanged lists of phrases and were given the task of finishing the thought, based on the logic of the proposed marker. After completing this task, the markers of formal style were repeated, and the students were given the task – to rework in groups the style of the created sentences, with the replacement of the discourse marker and possible adjustment of the vocabulary of the phrase. Later, paired versions of sentences - informal and formal, were presented to the group for evaluation and assessment for logical coherence, appropriate stylistic adaptation, and linguistic accuracy. This task evoked a lively emotional response, since it implied work and discussion in groups, and was remembered by the students for its creativity (as shown by the analysis of student questionnaires at the end of the semester).

For the topic of habits and states in the past using “used to” and “would”, the AI also offered several options for communication tasks, from which the following activities were formed through selection and adaptation:

- Memory line: students had to create several paired sentences in which they described their habits in the past (what they usually did or did not do, using used to, didn't use to, would), ending the phrases with information about whether they still have these habits now. This task turned into a spontaneous discussion, as someone shared additional information, students responded if their habits coincided, which involved everyone in the implementation of the task and discussion and caused a positive emotional response.

- Past vs Present Lifestyle: it was logical to propose in a group of students in the IT profile to compare people's lifestyles before and after the introduction of technical innovations (Internet, mobile communications, AI). The resulting discussion was interesting, as the students formulated not only general characteristics, but also shared personal experiences.

The effectiveness of these activities can be confidently affirmed as they successfully merge language objectives (grammar) with subject-specific knowledge (IT), implementing the CLIL approach [Dzulkurnain et al., 2024]; they transformed grammar learning into meaningful, contextualized interaction. Another key success factor was emotional engagement: personal anecdotes fostered a positive classroom atmosphere and lowered language barriers. Additional cognitive benefit was in form of dual focus on content and language, that as a result reinforced retention of studied material.

To practice conditional sentences of the first type in English, the AI offered several task options, of which the following were selected for the specific goals of the lesson and adapted to the group:

- Future Plans: since this topic was discussed towards the end of the 2nd semester, it was adapted in the graduating group to possible scenarios for the development of events in their lives: “What if you pass successfully/don't pass final exams?”, “You'll get your dream job, if...”, etc.

Students were offered different parts of sentences, which they supplemented in their own way. The relevance of the topic aroused interest and active discussion; it worked well due to linking grammar to pending graduation anxieties and aspirations, and also its cognitive depth, because it required weighing real-world consequences.

- Debate: First Conditional Arguments. The AI suggested choosing a controversial topic and dividing the students into two teams to hold a debate in which the arguments of both sides had to be in the form of sentences with the first conditional. The students themselves chose the topic for the debate ("Video Games: Beneficial or Harmful?"), which increased the emotional response of all group members and their interest in the discussion. As is generally noted in the professional literature: communicative tasks, especially debates, contribute to the development of critical thinking and communication skills in students [Ait Hattani, H., 2021].

The following conclusion can be drawn from the implementation of these tasks: they effectively combined grammatical and communicative practice with emotional involvement. The first task simulated real decision-making situations, where conditional sentences served as a tool for expressing hopes and fears (grammar as a thinking tool). The debates combined communicative intensity (required quick formulation of arguments in a given structure, which trained fluency), emotional response (relying on personal experience and opinions) and collaborative learning (working in teams, developing argumentation and listening skills).

Adapting learning tasks and materials to the specific needs of a group is a labor-intensive and time-consuming process. Using AI capabilities makes the teacher's job easier from the very first steps – planning the content and learning trajectory of the course. Questionnaires to identify learning needs before the start of a language course play a key role in creating a modern, inspiring and effective educational program. They help ensure that the course content fully meets the students' real needs, promotes a personalized approach and creates a solid foundation for sustainable progress and achieving high results [European Trade Union Institute [ETUI], n.d.]. As a result, when working with a group of fourth-year students majoring in mathematics and information technology as part of a one-year course in professional English, administering a diagnostic questionnaire became a necessity.

Using artificial intelligence tools, a questionnaire was developed that performs several key functions: identifying the educational needs and professional interests of students, determining preferred formats of educational activities. The analysis of questionnaire data allowed to form a teaching strategy, select educational materials (based on the ENGLISH for EVERYONE Level 4 teaching aid), and develop thematic planning taking into account the professional specifics of student training.

The instruction of this course incorporated AI technologies to address a critical didactic gap: whereas the standard textbook emphasized general language skills, learners required IT-tailored content. AI facilitated the creation of specialized supplementary assignments and development of adaptive teaching materials tailored to both educational needs and linguistic proficiency levels of learners.

One of the first requests for this group was for 5-10 minute speaking exercises for students majoring in IT. As a non-IT professional, I immediately liked the "Explain the Concept" assignment, in which each student had to choose a technical term or concept related to IT (e.g. "cloud storage," "data encryption," "machine learning") and describe it in simple, non-technical language. In this assignment, students demonstrated speaking skills, simplifying technical language, and clarity of concepts being explained.

When class time allowed, other tasks were also used, such as: "Tech News Debate", which discussed developments in the technology industry (e.g., the prospects for the development and use of AI in various fields), allowing students to demonstrate speaking, critical thinking, and persuasion skills; "Technical Troubleshooting", in which a common IT problem was chosen (e.g., "No Wi-Fi connection"), and students proposed possible troubleshooting steps. Overall, these tasks effectively linked language and profession, developing both linguistic and career-relevant skills of students.

Another example of an adapted task to practice using several adjectives in a description. The following activities were selected and modified from the options offered by the AI:

- Describe your favorite tech tool: Each student chose what they wanted to describe - their favorite software product, equipment, etc. - it was important to use as many adjectives as possible (general and specific opinion, size, age, shape, color, origin, material, purpose) and explain the benefit or uniqueness of the selected object of description.

- With the help of AI, it was also possible to generate a test task with several adjectives to describe software, gadgets, etc. It is worth noting that students were more interested in solving grammar problems where the vocabulary met their professional interests.

Both tasks turned an abstract grammar rule (e.g. natural use of adjective hierarchy) into a skill and expanded their professional vocabulary (targeted use of field-specific terms).

Conclusion:

The article systematically addresses three interconnected objectives in AI-enhanced language instruction: developing profession-specific task templates, designing AI-powered interactive assignments, and adapting lesson formats to maximize engagement.

The article provides strategies and examples for targeted content generation with the help of AI tools - DeepSeek, GigaChat, - that produce specifically focused exercises (IT), as well as workflow for adaptive materials: 1) needs assessment (pre-course surveys to identify student priorities), 2) AI customization (generated profession-oriented tasks), 3) teacher refinement (curated outputs for relevance/accuracy). The work also offers examples of implementation of AI-enhanced interactive assignments: debates, gamified activities that bring authentic language use in professional scenarios; showcase engaging lesson formats created with AI help: case studies linking language and IT, student-led video presentations on algorithms with AI-generated rubrics.

The article highlights the critical role of the teacher: while AI streamlines content creation, the need to oversee (filter irrelevant/inaccurate AI outputs), enhance (add cultural context or other nuances), and assess (clarity and accuracy) relies on the teacher.

The article presents evidence of efficacy of these strategies and student outcomes in form of increased motivation and improved skills in critical thinking, presentation, and technical communication: students showed higher levels of engagement with real-world tasks, also real-life profession-oriented projects bridged classroom-workplace gaps.

Key recommendations for teachers may include the following points: start with surveys to align AI tasks with student needs, ensure professional relevance, prioritize real-world applicability, and combine AI and human creativity. This structured integration of AI, as demonstrated in the article, enhances both language proficiency and career-readiness while preserving the teacher's pivotal role.

In conclusion, AI is a powerful tool for personalizing learning and creating adaptive learning paths; saving time on preparing for classes by creating assignments based on professionally oriented content using professional cases; increasing student motivation through the connection between language and specialty. At the same time, the use of AI is associated with certain risks: it is necessary to always check AI content, combine technology with teaching experience, critically evaluate AI materials and focus on the real needs of students. AI is a tool, not a replacement for a teacher.

Effective implementation of AI technologies in education requires conducting courses on training in its use among teachers, as well as courses on the correct policy for using AI tools among students.

As shown in the examples in this article, it is possible to start with simple technological solutions, exchanging experiences and evaluating new educational technologies.

While current and future technological advances may free up teachers' time and change classroom dynamics through automation, teachers are unlikely to be replaced by AI. Hopefully, educators will be able to focus on what they do best: teaching, inspiring, and supporting their students.

Prospects for **further research** include an in-depth study of the effectiveness of AI tools, in particular the long-term impact of AI on the quality of students' language skills; the development of

methods for integrating AI into educational processes, such as the creation of universal algorithms and guidelines for teachers on adapting AI content to different levels (A1-C2) and profiles (ESP, EAP); training teachers through courses on the effective use of AI (from basic skills to advanced adaptation of materials).

REFERENCES:

1. Ait Hattani, H. (2021). Communicative language teaching in support of critical thinking: The role of in-class debate. *Revue Linguistique et Référentiels Interculturels*, 2(1), 41–49. <https://revues.imist.ma/index.php/LIRI/article/download/27504/14397>
2. Bryant, J., Heitz, Ch., Sanghvi, S., Wagle, D. How artificial intelligence will impact K–12 teachers. January 14, 2020 <https://www.mckinsey.com/industries/education/our-insights/how-artificial-intelligence-will-impact-k-12-teachers#/>
3. Daud, A., Aulia, A. F., Muryanti, Harfal, Z., Nabilla, O., & Ali, H. S. (2025). Integrating artificial intelligence into English language teaching: A systematic review. *European Journal of Educational Research*, 14(2), 677-691. <https://doi.org/10.12973/eu-jer.14.2.677>
4. Dudeney, G., & Hockly, N. (2022). Artificial intelligence in English language teaching: Emerging trends and research. *ELT Journal*, 76(2), 123–133. <https://doi.org/10.1093/elt/ccab098>
5. Dzulkurnain, M.I., Iskandar, M... *Understanding the benefits and challenges of Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) in English education: a literature synthesis*. Journal on Education, Volume 06, No. 04, Mei-Agustus 2024. <https://jonedu.org/index.php/joe/article/view/5876>
6. EFL Cafe. (2024). *Integrating AI into the EFL/ESL curriculum: Lesson planning and implementation*. <https://eflcafe.net/integrating-ai-into-the-efl-esl-curriculum-lesson-planning-and-implementation/>
7. EFL Cafe. (2024, November 15). *Teaching EFL/ESL students effective English prompt crafting for AI-assisted learning*. <https://eflcafe.net/teaching-efl-esl-students-effective-english-prompt-crafting-for-ai-assisted-learning/>
8. European Trade Union Institute. (n.d.). *Assessing learners' needs and language level. Language training for European trade unionists - a guide*. <https://www.etui.org/sites/default/files/assessing%20needs.pdf>
9. Godwin-Jones, R. (2022). AI and language learning: Current realities and future possibilities. *Language Learning & Technology*, 26 (3), 1–13.
10. Holmes, W., Bialik, M., & Fadel, C. (2019). *Artificial Intelligence in Education: Promises and Implications for Teaching and Learning*. Center for Curriculum Redesign. <https://curriculumredesign.org/wp-content/uploads/AIED-Book-Excerpt-CCR.pdf>
11. Kukulska-Hulme, A. (2023). Artificial intelligence and language learning: Opportunities and challenges. *Language Learning & Technology*, 27(1), 1–15. <https://www.lltjournal.org/item/2023.01.01>
12. Luckin, R., Holmes, W., Griffiths, M., & Forcier, L. B. (2022). *Intelligence unleashed: An argument for AI in education*. Pearson. <https://www.pearson.com/content/dam/one-dot-com/one-dot-com/global/Files/about-pearson/innovation/open-ideas/Intelligence-Unleashed-Publication.pdf>